
Budgetary Behavior As An Instrument of Fiscal Federalism Efficiency: Does the Ethnicity-Tribalism Structure Matter?

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ABSTRACT

Fiscal federalism efficiency influence on local entity operations has recently gained tremendous recognition. However, the most surmountable challenge faced by majority developed-developing nations localities, is how to sustainably attain that fiscal credibility. Some theory-research-practice triangulation segments claim that fiscal federalism efficiency is easily achievable if entity budgetary behavior is well-managed. Others; notably those in the African setting, assert it is impractical without involving ethnicity-tribalism considerations. This research was an in-depth survey of budgetary behavior-fiscal federalism linkages in some Ugandan (East Africa)-based entities considering ethnicity-tribalism triangulation as a mediating factor. Its findings reveal that much as process control and manpower; key budgetary behavior attributes predict fiscal federalism efficiency, its other construct administrative machinery does not. Besides, the anticipated mediator; ethnicity-tribalism practices in the country's northern-eastern regional entities, plays no intervening role. Theory-literature-practice implications and future research path are systematically provided.

KEYWORDS: Local entity, fiscal federalism efficiency, budgetary behavior, ethnicity-tribalism system.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Currently numerous countries consider federalism the most ideal approach for managing public responsibilities. Federalism; or simply decentralization, is generally believed an exceptional mechanism in that direction on two critical grounds. First, it holds capacity to ably advance national unity and enhance regional economic disparities management at national level (Kyriacou, Muinelo-Gallo & Roca-Sagal'es, 2015). Second, at sub-national and particularly local government level, federalism formulation has over the years been found extraordinarily proficient in generating self-governance competences (Gemmell, Kneller & Sanz, 2013).

Accordingly, related research notably (Ríos, Bastida & Benito, 2016; Arellano & Bai, 2017), indicates that on the basis of these two considerations, globally various nations embrace fiscal federalism. As an offshoot of the foundation-federalism configuration, fiscal federalism has also been internationally adopted for its extraordinary effectiveness in managing public fiscal resources provided it is efficiently administered (Arellano & Bai, 2017).

Practically, fiscal federalism holds numerous related fiscal implications in regard to the multi-level government decentralized system it supports and is thus conventionally-associated with several attributes (Ríos et al., 2016). The most notable and salient inferences include: political-constitutional setup, local revenue-expenditure management, intergovernmental fiscal transfers (grants) control, inter-entity equalization, and resource management regulation (Gemmell et al., 2013).

The scholars; notably Kyriacou et al. (2015), posit that whenever these dimensions are transparently managed, controlled and promptly accounted-for periodically, reflects fiscal federalism efficiency attainment. However, sustainably realizing notable fiscal federalism efficiency-standards is often not an easy task (Kyriacou et al., 2015; Arellano & Bai, 2017). This challenge of failure to sustainably-achieve acceptable fiscal federalism efficiency ideals is very prevalent in developing countries-based localities. With the exception of only a few entities, the problem is remarkably extensive in Sub-Sahara African region (Gemmell et al., 2013).

Much as several studies have previously been conducted to establish what precisely explains the problem; consistent with fiscal federalism theory (Musgrave, 1983; Oates, 1999)practice triangulation, none of them is quite decisive on the matter. However, some scholars particularly (Matthew & Shah, 2005; Lee & Plummer, 2007; Saputra & Muda, 2017), attribute the fiscal-federalism-efficiency gaps to budgetary behavior obtaining in majority localities of such nations. Furthermore, other explorations such as the

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Otenyo and Lind (2004) / Dabla-Norris (2006) works, claim that the huge tribal-ethnic numbers and thus related fiscal perceptions are largely responsible for fiscal federalism efficiency complications particularly in African-based localities.

This particular research entailed an in-depth examination of budgetary behavior/ethnicitytribalism/fiscal federalism efficiency linkages in local governments located in the northern and eastern regions of Uganda. The East African country is a member of Inter-Governmental Authority for Development (IGAD), a popular organization for recently Sub-Saharan Africa federalized nations. The group comprises: Djibouti, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Kenya, Somalia, South Sudan, Sudan, and Uganda (Arellano & Bai, 2017).

For quite a long time, Uganda has been applauded for its fiscal-federalism-proficiency with its northern-eastern regional entities as exceptional performers (Afonso, Agnello & Furceri, 2010). Consequently, the investigation specifically focuses on these three fiscal federalism efficiency attributes predominant in recent research: constitutional-political set-up (Afonso et al., 2010; Hatfield, 2015), entity location (Gemmell et al., 2013), and resource generation (Arellano & Bai, 2017). Moreover, it is founded on and systematically-guided by numerous underpinnings in the fiscal federalism theory conceived and advanced by Musgrave (1983) and Oates (1999) respectively.

1.1. Study Relevance

This survey is considered novel, ideal, and therefore quite timely for contemporary fiscal federalism theory-literature-practice configuration. This is so on a number of grounds. First, it contextualizes related-theories; notably the fiscal federalism theory (Oates, 1999), to realities of fiscal federalism system in specifically developing nations such as those of the IGAD constituency. Thus, prospective scholars with intents of further-advancing the fiscal federalism theory and its applicability to African-based entity public finance operations will significantly benefit.

Second, much as an enormous literature profile on individual locality budgetary behavior/ ethnicity-tribalism structure/fiscal federalism efficiency (e.g. Matthew & Shah, 2005; Afonso et al., 2010; Arellano & Bai, 2017; Saputra & Muda, 2017) subsists, no study has so far investigated their apparent linkages. This point is a matter of reality in majority low-income and ethnicity-tribalism driven nations of the developing world, those of Sub-Saharan Africa being of no exception. Accordingly, by the research examining ethnicity-tribalism ties as a possible mediator in the perceptible budgetary behavior-fiscal federalism linkages, it presents a pioneering model in related literature.

Third, this exploration is equally appropriate for fiscal federalism practice as earlier observed in the Musgrave (1983)-Hatfield (2015) empirics specifically its foundation public finance-federalism policy. Entity authorities' decision-making procedures taken in regard to attaining fiscal federalism efficiency will consequently be implicated on realizing that budgetary behavior/ethnicity-tribalism framework is a pertinent dynamic. Thus, this will ultimately influence mandate and compliance to the parental public finance policy.

In sum, the current study bonds dots between local entity fiscal federalism efficiency theorizing and budgetary behavior connections, and apparent ethnicity-tribalism setup mediation influences from empirical and practice perspectives.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION, CONCEPTUALIZATION AND HYPOTHESES

The worldwide and decades-long federalism policy is largely driven by two-fold dimensions that practically motivate fiscal federalism espousal. Majority policy-settings appreciate the fact that sub-national entities; largely local governments, play host to numerous community groups (Muda, Mutia & Marhayanie, 2017). Moreover, these groups naturally hold equally-diverse perceptions and preferences for public services relevant for their survival and economic development. Thus, on the basis of these dual realities, taxation as a devise of revenue generation is administered and appropriate public services rendered (Lienert, 2013; Muda et al., 2017). From a theoretical context; notably the foundational fiscal federalism theory (Oates, 1999), it accordingly employs the foregoing realities to associate fiscal federalism with the resource allocation mandate. And as Oates (1999) specifically noted and later advanced by Arellano and Bai (2017), related theoretical-underpinnings attribute fiscal federalism efficiency to entity effective-resource-allocation.

This reality is practically exhibited by reduction in unemployment, effective provision of public services, and construction of development-relevant infrastructure such as health centers, schools, and road networks (Arellano & Bai, 2017). Furthermore; consistent with empirical evidence, individual entity constitutional-political mechanism (Afonso et al., 2010), location and site (Gemmell et al., 2013), and resource-generation capacity (Kyriacou et al., 2015) are pivotal for realizing requisite resource-allocation-standards effectively.

2.1. Fiscal Federalism Efficiency

2.1.1. The Constitutional/Political Mechanism-Entity Location-Resource Generation Traits Majority local governments employ constitutional-political structures, entity location, and resource-generation-capability considerations in order to realistically evaluate fiscal federalism efficiency. Afonso et al. (2010) and Hatfield (2015) postulate that localities which endeavor to strictly adhere to constitutional regulation, often deliver quality public services and by implication attain fiscal federalism efficiency.

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This empirical view confirms the fiscal- federalism-theoretical (Musgrave, 1983) perspective that constitutional compliance significantly enhances locality resource-allocation and accordingly fiscal federalism proficiency.

That standard is also feasible in institutions operating within moderately-mature partisanpolitics governments which tend to avoid ethnicity-tribalism discrimination. In Sub-Saharan African nations; Uganda inclusive, fiscal federalism efficiency has not been easy to attain due to constitutional and political set-up incapacitations (Gemmell et al., 2013; Hatfield, 2015). Likewise, literature equally emphasizes entity location as yet another fiscal federalism efficiency construct exceptionally crucial for operational requirements. Where a particular entity is geographically located reveals its resource-endowment structure and thus the regional horizontal fiscal imbalances considerations (Arellano & Bai, 2017). This consideration explains why localities with nominal capacity to generate sufficient local revenue; due to resourceendowment constraints, frequently pressurize central government (CG) for equalization grants.

Thus, as had earlier on been remarked by the Gemmell et al. (2013)-Arellano and Bai (2017) research, should CG not comply, inter-entity horizontal fiscal imbalances will be exacerbated and eventually undermine targeted entity fiscal federalism efficiency standards.

Furthermore, theory-research-practice configuration asserts that localities are also expected to be creative enough in generating resources in order to ably operate autonomously as the fiscal federalism mandate requires. Oates (1999)'s fiscal federalism theory emphasizes that sub-national units must; for instance, adopt technical manpower structures. Such mechanisms tremendously foster efficient implementation and monitoring of resource movements within the entity (Musgrave, 1983). Accordingly, Kyriacou et al. (2015) also point out that that type of competence enhances resource generation; particularly local revenue, pertinent for operational efficiency.

Moreover, Oates (1999) further posits that resource-generation is totally feasible if the entity-local community linkages are esteemed and society frequently sensitized on public service relevance. Given that relevant resources reside within the community, this relationship will not only enhance their allocation but will significantly empower realization of the fiscal federalism efficiency vision (Afonso et al., 2010; Oates, 1999).

2.2. Budgetary Behavior

Fiscal austerity and the need for strict observation of governing regulation has for long been emphasized by various governments especially in federalism settings. According to recent empirics (e.g. Matthew & Shah, 2005; Lee & Plummer, 2007; Ríos, Bastida & Benito, 2016), austerity in the country's fiscal configuration at both central and sub-national levels significantly augments strategic planning. Furthermore, it is a competence that catalyzes effective realization of political-economy performance (Saputra & Muda, 2017).

Contemporary public finance policy identifies the budget as the only trustworthy and practically-reliable instrument that can effectively generate fiscal austerity no matter its application location. Ideally, it is that management tool which is often employed to systematically-allocate organizational or government-owned fiscal resources. This is done in order to attain pre-determined operational goals in a more victorious manner (Lienert, 2013; Ríos et al., 2016).

Consistent with the Musgrave (1983) theoretical exposition, associated scholars; remarkably Muda et al. (2017), identify the budget as a very fundamental gadget for management control. This standard is particularly feasible as long as that fiscal apparatus is conceived and prepared in a technical way, approved, and ultimately implemented efficiently (Saputra & Muda, 2017). In practice, the three budgetary phases; preparation, approval, and implementation, nurture the possibility of either empowering or undermining ultimate attainment of public entity objectives. In a nutshell, it is the collective fluctuations in these segments which literature; notably the Lee and Plummer (2007)-Carlitz (2013)-Muda et al. (2017) setup, designates budgetary behavior.

Specifically, Muda et al. (2017) associate public entity budgetary behavior with operational motives and the mode the budgetary process is generally executed by responsible authorities. At sub-national level and particularly Sub-Sahara African-based localities, budgeting takes on two basic formalities often employed inter-changeably. These are: participatory budgeting and performance budgeting (Lee & Plummer, 2007; Muda et al., 2017).

On one hand, participatory budgeting is that joint decision-making process adopted by entities in order to enhance and promote pertinent fiscal accountability. Related research (e.g. Matthew & Shah, 2005), identify conventional budgetary policies with emphasis of furnishing accountability reports on a regular and sustainable basis. This is simply because given their significance in budgeting, prompt accountability practices tend to engender effective implementation and management of public-funded programs (Lee & Plummer, 2007).

On the other hand, various localities also prefer performance budgeting. As noted by Saputra and Muda (2017), performance budgeting is that reliable fiscal planning mechanism that ultimately breeds suitable budgetary-behavior standards. Furthermore, Muda et al. (2017) observe that much as performance budgeting is quite a complex undertaking, it simply requires fully-incorporating all relevant information for preparation-approval-implementation processes. Nevertheless, irrespective of the budgetary approach; participative or performance, adopted by the entity planning authorities, contemporary theory-research-practice

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triangulation identifies sub-national entity budgetary behavior with three basic attributes. These are: administration machinery (Oates, 1999; Matthew & Shah, 2005), process control (Musgrave, 1983; Ríos et al., 2016), and manpower (Oates, 1999; Lee & Plummer, 2007).

Notably; research, policy and practice (Lee & Plummer, 2007; Ríos et al., 2016) also proclaim that when these factors are properly managed and effectively monitored, fiscal federalism efficiency; especially in low-income localities, can easily be attained.

2.2.1. Entity Administration

Globally, local entities in majority fiscal federalism systems execute their administrative and public-service-delivery mandates based on constitutional and regulatory frameworks. The administrative set-up highlights locality organogram and specifies roles and responsibilities each category of manpower has to play (Matthew & Shah, 2005; Carlitz, 2013). Most importantly, however, what is extremely relevant is the modality adopted in constituting the personnel identification-deployment-control-supervision mechanism (Ríos et al., 2016).

Theory-research-policy configuration (e.g. Musgrave, 1983; Otenyo & Lind, 2004; Gemmell et al., 2013) largely asserts that: in mainstream African and specifically IGAD countries, entity administration is an exceptionally acute factor for budgetary behavioral trend. Given that they are nations often gripped by ethnicity-tribal divisionism, pre-mature partisan politics, rent-seeking and corruption practices, and widespread lack of fiscal management transparency, practical administration mechanisms engaged are habitually-compromised (Gemmell et al., 2013).

Accordingly, Otenyo and Lind (2004) indicate that entity administration gaps tend to frequently impair budgetary behavior and consequently targeted fiscal federalism efficiency. As stated in preceding sections, IGAD (Arellano & Bai, 2017), is quite a renowned assembly of various Sub-Saharan African nations which have of recent gone federalist. Djibouti, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Kenya, Somalia, South Sudan, Sudan, and Uganda constitute its current member-states (Afonso et al., 2010).

In majority Ugandan-based localities; for instance, largely 300 or so districts scattered in its seven geographical-regions, entity administration complications tremendously abound. Concerned intellects like Afonso et al. (2010), Gemmell et al. (2013), and Hatfield (2015) attribute the country's entity handicaps to geographical sectarianism and ethnicity-tribalism fractionalization. However, individual entity administrative capacities in especially its northern- eastern regions, have often escaped the rampant segregation malaise due to their low population sizes and transparency (Gemmell et al., 2013).

Furthermore, specifically Afonso et al. (2010) and Hatfield (2015), observe that these factors do not only augment the northern-eastern locality budgetary behavior, but partially explain their high standards of fiscal federalism efficiency relative to others in the country. Based on the foregoing entity administration-fiscal federalism efficiency configuration, we therefore proposed and tested the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 1: *Locality administration and fiscal federalism efficiency relate positively.*

2.2.2. Process Control

The budget as a financial instrument employed by majority corporate organizations, public institutions, and even government, is universally considered exceptionally-critical in enhancing cost efficiency and management operations control (Lienert, 2013; Saputra & Muda, 2017). Essentially, this tool serves as a fiscal mechanism displaying all projected revenue/income-expenditure structures anticipated to unfold in a targeted future period. As earlier indicated in the Lee and Plummer (2007) research, budgets also support managerial-administrative systems to evaluate manpower competences and performance achievements in the given financial period.

Collectively, the theory-research-practice structure (e.g. Oates, 1999; Kyriacou et al., 2015; Muda et al., 2017) identifies budgeting as a function of basically three foremost stages and which ideally constitute the budgetary process. These are: budget preparation, approval, and implementation. And as specifically noted in the Kyriacou et al. (2015) empirical work, fluctuations in any of these stages; particularly dysfunctional to budgetary goal-attainment if not appropriately managed, is what constitutes budgetary behavior.

Likewise, at sub-national and specifically local government level, budget process control also rests upon three fundamental factors. First, entity administration-financial staff budgetary competences driven by past experience, current operational realities, and likely future happenings (Carlitz, 2013). Second, the local revenue-generation capacity, central government grants adequacy; and in IGAD nations, donor support reliability (Lee & Plummer, 2007). The third dimension is the combined political influence and beneficiary community appreciation of past and current service delivery standards (Ríos et al., 2016; Saputra & Muda, 2017).

Consequently, in practice budget process-control remains largely a complex undertaking given that entities in mainstream federalized countries lack appropriate administrative-staff capacities to compose realistic budget formulations (Lee & Plummer, 2007). Moreover, most localities rarely mobilize and collect adequate enough local revenue to fund target recurrent budgets; a problem mostly exacerbated by generally-poor communities, from which the revenue is commonly generated (Arellano & Bai, 2017).

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Empirical evidence in related research; notably Gemmell et al. (2013), also reveals that central government grants; or inter-governmental fiscal transfers as they are common known, are released in form of unconditional, conditional, and equalization grants. Unconditional grants are meant to finance recurrent day-to-day operational budgets in support of the locally-generated resources. Localities can autonomously utilize these funds as per existant operational requirements and fiscal regulations (Dabla-Norris, 2006; Ríos et al., 2016).

According to Gemmell et al. (2013), central government policy also requires that conditional grants must be utilized strictly in accordance to pre-conceived outlay conditions and largely to finance infrastructural projects. Thus, much as such funds are managed by the local entity, the center comprehensively monitors their expenditure flow. The other form of fiscal release for locality development and service delivery requirements are equalization grants. Research such as the Matthew and Shah (2005)-Arellano and Bai (2017) set-up, supports the fiscal federalism theoretical observation that in various developing nations, equalization grants are quite rampant. Given that federal regions are never equitably resource-endowed; not only in fiscal terms but from technical competence and community sensitization perspectives as well (Ríos et al., 2016), IGAD-countries often engage equalization grants to effect inter-entity horizontal fiscal imbalances control and enhance regional development impartiality.

However, contemporary collective theory-research-fiscal federalism policy context maintains that in practice, these grants are rarely released to beneficiary localities in adequate amounts and quite promptly. Theorists (Musgrave, 1983; Oates, 1999), and Otenyo and Lind (2004)-Saputra and Muda (2017) research, attribute this widespread fiscal setback to dictation from majority nations' economic incapacitations. This proliferating practice does not only undermine entity budgetary behavior especially in regard to budget implementation, but tremendously prejudices fiscal-federalism efficiency (Saputra & Muda, 2017).

The IGAD member state; Uganda as a recently-federalized-nation, has not been an exception to this fiscal impairment over the years albeit it generally stands acclaimed for its fiscal federalism proficiency. Nevertheless literature; notably Afonso et al. (2010) and Muda et al. (2017), points out that relative to entities located in other regions of the country, majority of the northern-eastern region local governments, have often exhibited quite high fiscal federalism efficiency notches.

This is largely due to exceptional administration-staff competences and transparency in generating and managing their local revenues and received donor aid (Matthew & Shah, 2005; Muda et al., 2017). Thus, we found it empirically-logical to propose and analyze this related hypothesis:

Hypothesis 2: *Budget process control and fiscal federalism efficiency hold positive ties.*

2.2.3. Manpower

Viable and productive financial management systems at both corporate and public level largely rely on input from competent personnel. Such manpower is not only able to mobilize financial data and capture them in accounting records, but it tremendously enhances generation of reliable periodical financial reports and statements (Otenyo & Lind, 2004; Carlitz, 2013; Hatfield, 2015). The qualifications in question; according to Hatfield (2015) for instance, include academic and professional status, past experience, and likely-future competences.

Moreover, Carlitz (2013) also posits that in federalism systems in which fiscal federalism is a core construct oscillating around entity budgetary strength, qualified financial staff is a foundation requirement. This is simply because authorities heavily rely on personnel capacity to constitute entity budget desk; a planning structure of competent manpower considered knowledgeable in financial, economic, political, and society matters (Kyriacou et al., 2015). Consistent with the fiscal federalism theory (Oates, 1999), a robust budget desk is considered reliable in coordinating central government-locality-community fiscal concerns that do not only breed quality public service delivery, but most importantly enhances budgetary behavior (Saputra & Muda, 2017). Unfortunately, few local governments in developing nations; those of Sub-Saharan Africa and particularly IGAD inclusive, are able to transparently engage such quality budget desks.

Research evidence in Saputra and Muda (2017) work further reveals that most IGAD countries accord mandate to their respective localities to constitute autonomous human resource identification functions. Unfortunately, the rampant ethnicity/tribalism practices-partisan politics-poverty-rent seeking/corruption triangulation, betrays these efforts.

In Uganda, the Local Government Act (1988) (Afonso et al, 2010) requires that all local governments particularly districts manage sovereign District Service Commissions (DSC). The essence and responsibility of the DSC is to work hand-in-hand with entity human resource department in notably identifying and engaging appropriate manpower. With the exception of few localities; say those of the country's northern-eastern regions, budgetary behavior in the country's majority localities is often seriously questionable. The factor commonly cited is conventional budget desks-incompetent manpower (Matthew & Shah, 2005; Afonso et al, 2010).

In a nutshell, fiscal-federalism-efficiency is rarely achieved on acceptable standards not only in Ugandan-based localities but also in those of other IGAD nations due to manpowerbudget desk structural precincts. Guided by the preceding deliberations surrounding the apparent locality manpower-fiscal federalism efficiency networks, we were prompted to formulate the following hypothesis:

Hypothesis 3: *Entity manpower and fiscal federalism efficiency hold positive linkages.*

2.3. Ethnicity-Tribalism Structure

Fiscal federalism has been grossly embraced in federalism systems on several grounds. First, if governed competently, the technique encourages and effectively accords fiscal autonomy to subnational units. This opportunity granted to entities is not only extremely important for autonomous and sovereign planning, but breeds effective accomplishment of fiscal responsibilities (Gemmell et al., 2013; Muda et al., 2017).

Secondly, according to some other academics notably; Lienert (2013) and Hatfield (2015), fiscal federalism is also identified with exceptional capacity in engendering equity, transparency and accountability in sub-national entities particularly local governments. This conventional practice enables the entities to achieve their respective fiscal mandates in a more reliable manner.

Both fiscal federalism theory (Musgrave, 1983; Oates, 1999) and numerous research (e.g. Otenyo & Lind, 2004; Afonso et al., 2010; Carlitz, 2013), however, hold a collective view that the autonomy-equity-transparency-accountability configuration can easily be attained in environments with nominal cultural bias. Incidentally in majority of developing countries whether African, Asian, or South American-based, culture drives basic decision-making processes; fiscal or otherwise, due to parental ethnic-tribal setups (Afonso et al., 2010; Kyriacou et al., 2015).

Evidence in the Afonso et al. (2010) research; for instance, indicates that particularly in the African setting; that of the IGAD nations inclusive, ethnicity and tribalism have tremendously affected creation of the would-be viable districts and related local governments. As a result, generation of sufficient local revenue and effective control and management of grants or donorfunding are often undermined by lack of transparency and accountability arising from such practices. Consequently, much as central governments endeavor to accord some level of autonomy and equity, required levels of fiscal federalism efficiency are rarely attained in majority local entity locations (Carlitz, 2013).

As a typical example, ethnicity-tribalism influences in Uganda have frequently compelled central government to create numerous local governments. This is regardless of their capacity to effectively manage fiscal resources for quality public service delivery (Dabla-Norris, 2006). For political reasons; as recently posited by Arellano and Bai (2017), the center also creates more districts in order to secure more votes in future. This is no matter whether prospective entity budgetary-behavioral-capacity and ultimate fiscal-federalism-efficiency outcomes will meet required standards or not.

Grounded on such exposure and surrounding previous research evidences, the following hypothesis was therefore proposed and accordingly subjected to statistical testing: **Hypothesis 4:** *In local government, ethnicity-tribalism arrangement mediates budgetary behavior-fiscal federalism efficiency connectivity.*

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Participants and Procedures

In order to execute an effective test of the current study's hypothesized model, a set of survey packages was engaged. The instruments were systematically disseminated to administrators and employees of the numerous districts, municipalities and sub-counties comprising the northern and eastern regions of Uganda.

As previous social science research (e.g. Yuan, Hayashi & Yanagihara, 2007; Renaud & Victoria-Feser, 2010; Ghozali, 2013) recommends this approach was embraced because collecting survey data from different units of analysis and inquiry significantly expedites study predictor evaluation. Moreover, the methodology likewise augments the outcome variable of the current model. Ultimately it then renders related potential same data sauce-bias effects extremely marginal and therefore very relevant (Renaud & Victoria-Feser, 2010).

Thus, based on a purposively and randomly-selected sample (Mathieu, DeShon & Bergh, 2008), a total of 440 structured questionnaires were initially administered to the identified entity participants. In response, 430 instruments were received back; depicting a methodologically acceptable response rate of (≥ 0.75) (Yuan et al., 2007; Sharma & Kim, 2013).

Resultant descriptive statistics reveal the following respondent biographical set-up: 57% male and 43% female; mean age (36-40) years with (7.52) standard deviation; 64% married, single 24% and others 12%; 68% hold bachelors or higher educational degrees; and 63% had served in their respective positions for (6-10) years.

From a practice perspective, these data suggest that surveyed entities execute largely gender-balanced activities enforced by a mature and family-responsible workforce. As also indicated in the Sharma and Kim (2013) research, such a structure indicates possibility and ease in achieving entity objectives. Additionally; relative to that in other IGAD nations, the above statistical-findings also suggest that the investigated Ugandan-based locality manpower is quite educated and well-experienced in their work. In sum, with such a human resource backing, the entities can easily realize their fiscal federalism efficiency vision.

3.2. Measures

This study's variable constructs were measured by various-item scales whose dimensions oscillated from 1=Strongly Disagree to 5=Strongly Agree. As recommended by related literature (e.g. Mathieu et al., 2008; Ghozali, 2013), the number of items adopted to verify construct- substantiality must be a function of the construct saliency as per existant theory-research-practice direction.

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3.2.1. The Constitutional/Political Mechanism-Entity Location-Resource Generation Traits The first fiscal federalism efficiency attribute; community-political mechanism, was measured using a 10-item scale; (reliability coefficient status: $\alpha = 0.86$), modified from those in the Afonso et al. (2010)-Hatfield (2015) surveys. One of such items runs as follows: “In this local government, community-political linkages significantly enhance fiscal federalism efficiency.”

Another scale comprising 8 items and generated; but systematically-adjusted from the Gemmell et al. (2013) work, was engaged in assessing the entity location construct. A typical item from the ($\alpha = 0.79$) scale stated that: “This entity’s location and regional site has over the years contributed to its fiscal federalism dysfunction.” The concept resource-generation was evaluated by another 8-item scale related to the methodological structure in the Arellano and Bai (2017) research. The item “There is no need to emphasize generation in this locality” comprises one of the ($\alpha = 0.81$) scale.

3.2.2. Entity Administration-Process Control-Manpower Constructs

As one of the most significant components of local entity budgetary behavior, entity administration was measured by a scale comprising 14 items. The scale; accordingly modified from a related one employed by Matthew and Shah (2005), exhibited an ($\alpha = 0.84$) reliability quantity. Its assessment items includes: “Entity budgetary direction rarely relies on administrative machinery.”

The other attribute; process control, was verified using a 13-item scale ($\alpha = 0.72$) similar to that in the Ríos et al. (2016) investigation. One of the items states: “When the budget process is properly controlled, its ultimate behavior is automatically guaranteed.”

Finally, manpower element was assessed on the basis of 12 items including: “Since personnel are often easy to compromise, its role in budgetary behavior is negligible.” The item scale ($\alpha = 0.76$) content was founded on that in the empirics of Lee and Plummer (2007) but of course systematically-adjusted.

3.2.3. Ethnicity-Tribalism System

One of the most critical objectives of the current study was to establish whether community ethnicity-tribalism conduct actually mediates claimed locality budgetary behavior-fiscal federalism efficiency linkages. Accordingly, a 15-item scale ($\alpha = 0.84$) akin to that in the Otenyo and Lind (2004) / Dabla-Norris (2006) surveys but systematically-amended, was adopted to assess entity ethnicity-tribalism coordination. “This local government often disregards ethnicity and tribalism influences in its budgetary activities” was one of the scale contents.

3.3. Control Variables Management

Simulation studies such as the: Yuan et al. (2007)-Mathieu et al. (2008)-Hair, Black, Babin and Anderson (2010)-Renaud and Victoria-Feser (2010)-Sharma and Kim (2013) grouping, assert that some research variables with extraordinary effects must always be controlled for. This is simply because if ignored, their influence especially on hypothesis analysis, often tends to bias and seriously compromise ultimate results (Mathieu et al., 2008; Sharma & Kim, 2013). In compliance to that advice, we therefore controlled for key participant-biographical attributes namely: gender, age, marital status, educational level, position held, and period served. Likewise, all latent variables adopted to supplement confirmatory factor analysis were also controlled for. As specifically posited by Hair et al. (2010), biographical identities often impair inter-variable relationship statistical analysis results while; despite their relevancy in instrument validity verification, latent variables have a tendency of biasing hypothesis-test grades.

4. ANALYTICAL PATH

The four hypotheses declared in the study were statistically-tested using both regression analysis (Hair et al., 2010; Renaud & Victoria-Feser, 2010) and multi-variant structural equation modeling (SEM) (Ghozali, 2013; Sharma & Kim, 2013) techniques.

As per both descriptive and inferential statistics-based explorations; notably Hair et al. (2010) suggests, data collection instrument: reliability/inter-variable correlations/participant biographical attributes, must be first verified before testing stated hypotheses. Thus, this methodological parentage was strictly observed by engaging the conventional SPSS package in order to effectively establish respective statistical stands. Furthermore, Analysis of Moments Structures (AMOS); another acclaimed simulation software (Yuan et al., 2007), then supported the SEM procedures relevant for hypothesis scrutiny.

Typically, SEM is comprised of two basic models: measurement model and structural model (Ghozali, 2013; Mathieu et al., 2008). The measurement model; built on robust confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) results, enhances generation of reliable variable direct/indirect effects assessment results. However, such results are only reliable after controlling for any adopted latent factors and if the model’s goodness of-fit indices are quite modest (Mathieu et al., 2008).

Its counterpart; the structural model, supports verification of the study’s endogenous/exogenous construct connections. Yuan et al. (2007) also associate this model with the capacity to furnish target indirect (mediation) effect statistics in a proficient manner as long as it is properly managed.

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5. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

5.1. Instrument Reliability-Respondent Biographics-Variable Correlations Structure Inconsistencies in data-collection instruments; notably questionnaires and interview guides, often compromise data analysis results. Accordingly, related research (e.g. Hair et al., 2010-Kyriacou et al., 2015), suggests that before executing any descriptive, inferential and hypothesis statistical analysis, the instruments should always be subjected to reliability-validity tests first.

Accordingly, the instrument’s reliability status was initially verified. Statistical results (Table 1), reveal acceptable Cronbach alpha coefficients (Gemmell et al., 2013) [$(\alpha = 0.70) - (\alpha = 0.89)$] range for its numerous variables and related data.

Thereafter, participant-biographies: gender, age, marital status, educational level, position and period served, were investigated and then systematically-controlled for. Table 1 associated statistical analysis results stand as follows: Gender: (F 43%, M 57%); Age Bracket: [(20-25) 9%; (26-30) 17%; (31-35) 23%; (36-40) 43%; (41+) 8%]; Marital Status: (Single 24%; Married 64%; Others 12%); Education: (Certificate 5%; Diploma 27%; Degree+ 68%); Period Served: [(1-5) 12%; (6-10) 63%; (11+) 25%]; n=430.

Table 1: Variable Means, Standard Deviations, Reliability Coefficients, and Correlations

#	Variable Item	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	EnttyAd. Machinery	3.08	1.541	.87								
2	Process Control	3.07	1.534	.49**	.81							
3	Manpower	3.09	1.552	.32*	.38**	.83						
4	Budgetary Behavior	3.02	1.545	.37*	.28*	-.31**	.78					
5	Ethnicity + Tribalism	3.23	1.578	.31**	-.33*	.27*	.39*	.85				
6	ConstPolitical Set-up	3.12	1.556	-.29*	.34**	.31	.37**	.17*	.88			
7	Entity Location	3.01	1.533	.35**	.28	.44*	.33	.31*	.36**	.75		
8	Resource Generation	2.76	1.499	.36*	.32*	-.35**	.28*	-.34**	.39	.34*	.84	
9	Fiscal Fed. Efficiency	3.05	1.504	.41**	-.30*	.43	.37**	.28*	.38*	.29**	.37	.82

Notes: EnttyAd. Machinery = Entity Administrative Machinery; ConstPolitical Set-up = Constitutional and Political Set-up; Fiscal Fed. Efficiency = Fiscal Federalism Efficiency; **Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed); Reliability coefficients in parenthesis; n=430.

From the foregoing respondent-biographical statistics contents, it can also be observed that investigated entities assert gender-balance policy. Moreover, majority of their personnel hold family responsibilities and are quite well-educated albeit middle-aged. Theory-researchfiscal policy (Oates, 1999; Otenyo & Lind, 2004; Matthew & Shah, 2005; Arellano & Bai, 2017) structure associates such manpower with efficient and transparent fiscal responsibility execution.

Table 1 results also exhibit inter-variable and construct mean, standard deviation, and correlation coefficient values. These statistics designate that the variables and their constructs hold largely moderate mean [2.76 - 3.23] and standard deviation [1.499 - 1.578] contents.

Consistent with conventional methodology (e.g. Renaud & Victoria-Feser, 2010; Sharma & Kim, 2013), related correlations are likewise not only significant at both [0.01] and [0.05] levels; 2-tail direction, but fall within the recommended [(-0.30) - (0.49)] assortment.

Just to highlight the statistical-practical implications of some few selected items; for instance, the predictor budgetary behavior positively and significantly relates with entity fiscal federalism efficiency and ethnicity-tribalism structure. This is to the extent of

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[$r = 0.37, p < 0.01$] and [$r = 0.39, p < 0.05$] respectively. The implication is that should entity budgetary behavior improve by (37%) and (39%), fiscal federalism efficiency and ethnicity-tribalism standards will also respectively progress by similar magnitudes.

On the contrary, entity administrative mechanisms hold negative [$r = -0.29, p < 0.05$] albeit significant linkages with the constitutional-political environment in which they operate. As earlier driven by the Musgrave (1983)'s fiscal federalism theory, the bio-factors in majority subnational entities often relate in opposite directions. This therefore implies that whenever the localities try to overhaul their administrative systems to; say (29%), the governing constitutionalpolitical mindsets often decline by the same level; a situation Muda et al. (2017) pinch to majority IGAD localities.

5.2. Hypothesis Analysis: Direct and Mediation Effects

Structural equation modeling and specifically its measurement-model was engaged in scientifically-testing this research's four hypotheses. However, as recommended in past simulation surveys; notably (Yuan et al., 2007; Sharma & Kim, 2013), the model must first display moderately significant item-loadings and reasonable goodness-of-fit indices before adoption. These standards are critical for reliable hypothesis analysis results.

Factor loadings and goodness-of-fit indices for the model employed in this study stand as follows: Chi-Square (χ^2/df) = .296; $df = 1$; $p = .586$; (χ^2/df) = .296; GFI = .984; NFI = .998; RFI = .983; IFI = 1.004; TLI = 1.044; CFI = 1.000; RMSEA = .016 [L.000; H.104] at 90. Academics Sharma and Kim (2013); for instance, associate such statistics with quite trustworthy hypothesis direct-indirect effects test results.

Furthermore, the investigation's measurement model was subjected to confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). This helps establish the common methods variance (CMV)/multi-collinearity threats status often affecting study variables. Ghazali (2013) posits that; in particular, CFA-aided Harman's single factor technique empowers verification of both CMV and research instruments' construct-discriminant validity.

Multi-collinearity assessment is critical for establishing unusual inter-variable correlations that often hamper hypothesis analysis authenticity. However, Yuan et al. (2007) caution that: in order to clearly portray dataset tolerable CMV threat, goodness-of-fit indices in the Harman's one factor structure must be weak compared to those in the SEM-based measurement model.

Table 2: Hypothesis Analysis

Dependent Variable: Fiscal Federalism Efficiency					
Particulars	β	SE	t	TV	VIF
SEM Analysis Results: Direct Effects					
Administrative System → Fiscal Federalism Efficiency	-.432*	.213	1.152	.776	1.288
Process Control → Fiscal Federalism Efficiency	.331**	.232	1.596	.725	1.380
Manpower → Fiscal Federalism Efficiency	.176**	.211	1.845	.838	1.194
Indirect [Mediation] Effect Budgetary Behavior → Ethnicity-Tribalism Status → Fiscal Federalism Efficiency					
SEM Analysis Results	-.518*	.149	1.337	.679	1.247
Bootstrap Results: Adjusted R² [0.726]; 95% CI [-0.031] ↔ [0.010]					

Notes: SE = Standard Error; TV = Tolerance Value; VIF = Variable Inflation Factor; Standardized Beta Coefficients Reported; * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; Bootstrap Sample Size = 2000; CI = Confidence Interval; Hypotheses Status: Hypothesis 1[Not Supported]; Hypothesis 2[Supported]; Hypothesis 3[Supported]; Hypothesis 4[Not Supported]; $n = 430$.

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As presented earlier, this research's measurement-model-indices stand as follows: Chi-Square (χ^2/df) = .296; $df = 1$; $p = .586$; (χ^2/df) = .296; GFI = .984; NFI = .998; RFI = .983; IFI = 1.004; TLI = 1.044; CFI = 1.000; RMSEA = .016 [L.000; H.104]. Relatively, the indices were much stronger than those in the Harman's single factor model: ($\chi^2 = 418.566$; $df = 327189$; $\chi^2/df = 1.280$; IFI = 0.758; TLI = 0.441; CFI = 0.519; RMSEA = 0.108; L.126, H.493). This now implies that the study's data were not under any serious common-methods- variance threat (Yuan et al., 2007).

Sharma and Kim (2013) also identify inter-variable/construct tolerance values (TV) and variance inflation factors (VIF) as robust signals of potential multi-collinearity hazards. When the [(TV < 1.00) - (VIF < 10.0)] benchmark is attained, it denotes quite fair constructdiscriminate validity standards of the data collection instrument. As displayed in Table 2, this survey's [TV-VIF] profile satisfies the recommended empirical standards in respect to both multi-collinearity threat and instrument validity requirements.

5.2.1. Hypothesis Direct Effects Analysis

On the basis of its theory-literature-policy foundation, it had been proposed as Hypothesis 1 of this study that in local government, entity administrative system holds a positive relationship with fiscal federalism efficiency standards. On the contrary, related Table 2 multivariatestructural equation-modeling (SEM) results; [$\beta = -.432$, $p < .05$, t -value 1.152], indicate that data collected from surveyed Ugandan-based localities could not support that proposition.

However, data sustained both Hypothesis 2 and Hypothesis 3 projections. It had been predicted under Hypothesis 2 that in such entities, budgetary process control relates positively with fiscal federalism efficiency and as Hypothesis 3, that manpower also holds a positive association with fiscal federalism efficiency. Respectively, the SEM statistical results stand as follows: [$\beta = .331$, $p < .01$, t -value 1.596]; [$\beta = .176$, $p < .01$, t -value 1.845].

5.2.2. Mediation Effect Analysis

Numerous empirical studies; not only in social sciences but also in other disciplines, hold one common methodological viewpoint: that much as research problems are often a victim of mediating-moderating factor influences, it is not easy to systematically identify and quantify that effect (Yuan et al., 2007; Mathieu et al., 2008; Sharma & Kim, 2013).

In this particular investigation, it had been propositioned as Hypothesis 4 that: ethnicitytribalism practices that dominate majority Sub-Saharan Africa IGAD societies, mediate apparent local entity budgetary behavior-fiscal federalism efficiency linkages. Drawing input from the Baron-Kenny (1986)/Preacher-Hayes (2008) mediation effect analysis approaches; as highlighted in the [(Yuan et al., 2007)-(Ghozali, 2013)-(Sharma & Kim, 2013)] empirics, both conventional SEM and bootstrapping techniques were therefore adopted to execute the relevant tests.

Table 2 SEM-based mediation analysis results [$\beta = -.518$, $p < .05$, t -value 1.337] suggest that ethnicity-tribalism practices hold no mediation effect on budgetary behavior-fiscal federalism efficiency connections in surveyed localities. This outcome was confirmed by resubjecting the available data to a more robust bootstrapping methodology emphasized in the Yuan et al. (2007)-Sharma and Kim (2013) works. Related bootstrap results; based on 2000 subsamples, also display a no-mediation-effect arrangement from a 95% bias-corrected-confidence- interval (CI) of [-0.031] \leftrightarrow [0.010]. Additionally, this finding was backed-up by an equally resolute Adjusted-R² [0.726] value (Hair et al., 2010) suggesting that in practice, budgetary behavior predicts the fiscal federalism efficiency mechanism to an extent of 73%.

6. FINDINGS DISCUSSION

Relating the foregoing findings of the survey to governing theory-literature-practice formulation, they breed a more-or-less endless empirical debate. Admittedly; as both Musgrave (1983) and Oates (1999) postulate in the fiscal federalism theory, sustainably attaining acceptable fiscal federalism efficiency standards, is an uphill task. This obligation remains a big challenge to majority localities not only in developing but in developed nations as well (Oates, 1999; Kyriacou et al., 2015).

As stated earlier, a number of contemporary studies attribute the prediction of related changes in fiscal federalism efficiency to budgetary behavior. Notably, Matthew and Shah (2005), Lee and Plummer (2007), and recently Saputra and Muda (2017) emphasize entity administrative system, process control, and manpower capacity; key budgetary behavior attributes, as critical fiscal federalism efficiency predictors.

On the basis of the (Matthew & Shah, 2005-Saputra & Muda, 2017) opinions, for instance, it had been projected as Hypothesis 1 of this research that entity administrative mechanism holds a positive relationship with fiscal federalism efficiency. Incidentally, its data render no backing to that prediction. Lack of data support to the proposition sort of upholds the Gemmell et al. (2013) observation that administrative systems in majority IGAD-based entities rarely benefit fiscal-federalism-efficiency endeavors.

According to Musgrave (1983) and Gemmell et al. (2013), most administrative systems cannot augment fiscal federalism efficiency effectively simply because they are often denied operational independence. In majority IGAD local governments; those of Uganda inclusive, ethnicity-tribalism dimensions and pre-mature partisan-politics tremendously undermine administrative

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structures and ultimately fiscal federalism efficiency. Other factors include rentseeking/corruption abnormalities and fiscal management-transparency deficiency (Gemmell et al., 2013).

Under Hypothesis 2, we had also anticipated that budgetary process control positively associates with locality fiscal federalism efficiency. Consistent with evidence in the Lee and Plummer (2007) research, data employed in this investigation ratified that view. Practically, this implies that if resource-constrained entities; those of IGAD inclusive, continue to bear budgetary regulations, they are likely able to realize the fiscal federalism efficiency dream. Scholars Afonso et al. (2010) attribute fiscal federalism efficiency achievement in Uganda's northerneastern regional localities to strict budgetary process controls observance and rent-seeking and corruption practices avoidance.

Moreover, survey data also reinforced Hypothesis 3 prediction that entity fiscal federalism efficiency and manpower setup hold a positive relationship. As Saputra and Muda (2017) previously indicated, institutional personnel play a vital role in attainment of operational goals. It is therefore of little doubt that proficient manpower in federalized entities such as those of IGAD and Uganda in particular, does not only empower budgetary behavior, but tremendously augments fiscal federalism efficiency (Afonso et al., 2010).

Finally, other investigations (e.g. Otenyo & Lind, 2004; Dabla-Norris, 2006) claim that much as entity budgetary behavior may be influential to the attainment of its fiscal federalism efficiency aspiration, surrounding ethnicity-tribalism linkages play a very noteworthy role to that effect. The assertion prompted the formulation of this research's Hypothesis 4: Ethnicitytribalism structure mediates budgetary behavior-fiscal federalism efficiency connections in local government.

However, contrary to the (Otenyo & Lind, 2004/Dabla-Norris, 2006) formulation, this proposal failed to secure support from basic data. Admittedly, all societies in Sub-Saharan Africa IGAD member states are driven by culture emanating from ethnicity-tribal configurations. Otenyo and Lind (2004) associate these societies with a common belief that economic development; especially drawn from public service delivery, must be that extracted from ethnicity-tribal federalized systems. This type of mindset explains why most local governments in such countries are often created on ethnic-tribal basis.

Data employed in this research could not back-up the budgetary behavior/ethnicitytribalism setup/fiscal federalism efficiency mediation proposal simply because; as stated by Afonso et al. (2010), ethnicity-tribalism practices in Uganda's northern-eastern regions are very minimal. Besides, District Service Commissions in majority of the region's entities operate autonomously of ethnicity-tribalism influences and often emphasize quality service delivery and fiscal accountability (Muda et al., 2017).

7. THEORY-LITERATURE-PRACTICE IMPLICATIONS AND STUDY LIMITATIONS

Findings generated from this investigation are likely to impact foundational theory, literature, and fiscal federalism practice and policy. After critically evaluating prevalent global fiscal federalism practices for quite some time, Musgrave (1983) formulated the fiscal federalism theory. The theory; later advanced by Oates (1999), specifically stresses entity fiscal autonomy, accountability transparency, technical competences, and quality service delivery to beneficial communities.

Nevertheless, much as the Musgrave (1983)-Oates (1999) formulations were conceived in the developed world setting, it largely appears as though they were designed to principally benefit and overhaul the poor, resource-constrained, and largely corrupt developing world localities. The essence of this research is to advance the reality that the Musgrave (1983)-Oates (1999) theoretical motives are also applicable in developing nations' fiscal federalism environments. Thus, if properly implemented, outcomes from target fiscal federalism efficiency vision are absolutely feasible.

Literature and particularly fiscal federalism knowledge body will benefit from this survey on two basic grounds. First, the analysis links fiscal federalism theory with locality budgetary behavior/ethnicity-tribalism practices/fiscal federalism efficiency triangulation. This quite unique and possibly novel innovation, will specifically impact related research in other developing countries. Second, the study critically examines the possibility of ethnicity-tribalism activities mediation influence in the fiscal federalism efficiency attainment endeavors. Much as these practices have been previously held obvious-imaginings (Otenyo & Lind, 2004; Dabla-Norris, 2006), the study findings reveal a contrary empirical context.

Fiscal federalism practice and particularly governing policy (see Lienert, 2013; Gemmell et al., 2013), have been challenged by this study findings to always act flexibly in executing locality fiscal mandates. As earlier stressed by Oates (1999)'s fiscal federalism theory; for instance, applied regulations must be cognitive of local community public service realities and manpower capacity. Moreover, operational factors such budgetary systems and the ethnicitytribalism-politics that commonly impair standard fiscal federalism structures, must be handled responsibly (Hatfield, 2015).

However, despite the foregoing theory-literature-practice implications, the study is not absolutely comprehensive but was encircled with a series of empirical handicaps. Notably, it was conducted in Uganda; an IGAD-member state, whose localities may not have provided all the data relevant for effectively-executing such a sensitive exploration. This is more so given that the methodological approach employed; namely, cross-sectional research design (Renaud & Victoria-Feser, 2010) is snapshot in nature. In addition, the study was conducted during the challenging Covid-19 epidemic period. Resultant entity lockdowns affected

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businesses, employment, and even families. This is likely to have significantly impaired respondent reactions to data submission requirements.

8. FUTURE RESEARCH PATH

Regardless of societal dynamics, academic investigations continue to be executed in all countries throughout the world. We thus propose that future studies; especially those surrounding the fiscal-federalism-efficiency problem, embrace a much broader approach such as longitudinal research design (Hair et al., 2010; Ghozali, 2013) to come up with a broader picture thereof.

Besides, prospective inquiries should also handle inevitable health challenges such as those imposed by the Covid-19 circumstantially on nation-by-nation and entity-by-entity basis. This is feasible if, say, appropriate data collection techniques such as those involving virtual procedures are adopted.

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